

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND ITS IMPACT ON ORGANIZATIONAL EFFICIENCY SUCCESS BY MEDIATING TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT (AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF A SAMPLE OF IRAQI PRIVATE COLLEGES IN BAGHDAD)

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Abstract

Organizational culture practices, as a contemporary and advanced management concept, have received significant attention from researchers in business administration and strategic management. This is because it serves colleges by adopting the Total Quality Management (TQM) philosophy, which helps them chart their organizational path and ensure their existence by seizing the best market opportunities and confronting environmental threats, thus successfully fulfilling their mission in Iraqi society. The main objective of the study is to verify and empirically test the impact of organizational culture on TQM, which supports ways to achieve organizational effectiveness through the criteria of effectiveness and efficiency in the performance of Iraqi private colleges, leading to the presentation of important ideas, proposals, and recommendations for decision-makers. The study proposed several hypotheses, the most prominent of which is that "the strategic leadership of senior management in Iraqi private colleges has a positive and significant impact on effectiveness as a requirement for organizational effectiveness," and on efficiency as a requirement for effectiveness again, with the presence of total quality management as an effective mediating variable. The study adopted the descriptive-analytical approach as a method that harnesses the obtained qualitative data and converts them into quantitative indicators by designing a standard questionnaire to measure the three variables (strategic leadership, total quality management, and organizational success), which was distributed to a deliberate random sample of faculty members consisting of (284) instructors, working in (7) private colleges in the capital, Baghdad. The hypothesized relationships were tested in the conceptual model prepared for this purpose from the data that were collected and analyzed using several statistical methods, and adopting advanced computer programs, such as the statistical program for the social sciences (SPSS V.25), and the structural equation modeling technique for partial least squares (SEM-PLS).

Keywords: Exploring Core Competencies, Organizational Success, TQM.

THE INTRODUCTION

Organizational culture is one of the most important internal dimensions of an organization, determining its effectiveness. As management consultant Peter Drucker famously said, "Culture eats strategy for breakfast" (Hyken, 2015). He meant that organizational culture is more influential than strategy by motivating employee behavior, beliefs, internal and external relationships, and the way they work. This is because culture is based on values, despite the importance of strategy and other internal dimensions (Schein, 2010).

Culture represents an organization's identity and is considered by many to be its fundamental structure. The vision, values, and mission of administrative leaders determine the approach at the top of the administrative hierarchy. This, in turn, is reflected in the ethics and legal

foundations, which form a model for the way administrative leaders and other employees operate and behave (Cameron & Quinn, 1999).

The Competing Values Framework (CVF) is one of the models used to study the suitability of an organization and its culture to its surrounding work environment and conditions. It has been tested for several decades, and it has been shown that the effectiveness criteria proposed by this model have positively impacted the suitability of an organization's culture to the elements and characteristics of its external work environment (Cameron & Quinn, 2006).

Research problem

The main topic of this study is to analyze organizational culture in universities and to understand the relationship between organizational culture patterns and organizational effectiveness. This research problem emerged for the researcher through her review of the literature and studies that addressed the topic of organizational culture, organizational effectiveness, and total quality management, and her understanding of their importance in determining the efficiency and effectiveness of institutions. The researcher aims to arrive at a study whose results can contribute to developing the administrative apparatus of government institutions. This study attempts to answer this question: Is it possible to analyze the organizational culture in Iraqi universities in relation to organizational effectiveness, using the approaches of the organizational culture analysis model developed by Robert Quinn Kim Cameron & based on the theory of competing values. the study problem emerged through the following research question:

What is the impact of exploring core competencies on organizational success through TQM?

This main question includes the following sub-questions:

1. Is there a correlation between core competencies and organizational efficiency?
2. Is there a relationship of influence between core competencies in achieving organizational effectiveness?
3. How can the organizations under study successfully employ and invest in core competencies to develop and achieve organizational success?

Research hypotheses

The research hypotheses are as follows:

Main hypothesis

There is no direct significant relationship between exploring core competencies and organizational success mediated by TQM, and the following sub-hypotheses emerge from it:

The first sub-hypothesis: There is a direct, positive, and significant relationship between Organizational culture and organizational efficiency.

Sub-hypothesis: There is a direct, positive, and significant relationship between human competence and organizational effectiveness.

Sub-hypothesis: The core competencies of senior management have a strong direct and significant relationship with TQM.

The importance of the research and its essential objectives

The importance of the study lies in its assistance in discovering and identifying the most important activities, events, and policies that support the success of private university education, represented by private colleges in Iraq. These activities can support the achievement of their expected strategic and operational objectives in general, as well as those related to the personal and life goals of faculty members. At the same time, it focuses on the most important positive elements embedded in these activities and their beneficial impact on the efficiency and effectiveness of organizational performance.

Hence, the economic importance of the study emerges through the successful implementation of the strategic vision of private colleges in a way that helps them exploit investment opportunities in the higher education and scientific research market, ways to retain existing customers, attract new customers in the long term, increase their market share, and improve their profitability. Furthermore, it helps them avoid numerous threats and confront environmental challenges, leading to their growth and development, and ensuring their survival in the changing and highly competitive university business environment in Iraq.

Previous studies

The researcher examined studies that have been researched and are relevant to exploring core competencies and their impact on organizational success, as follows:

(Yaqoub, 2024) The study aims to verify the extent to which companies have opportunities to achieve organizational success through their ability to deal with environmental changes in a responsive or proactive manner. The research problem is crystallized in the weakness of mechanisms and indicators for determining clear and precise standards for tourism companies that are described as organizationally successful, and most studies are limited to studying the impact of personal characteristics of the management team on achieving organizational success. The research sample consisted of (204) observations from global management teams in tourism companies in the city of Baghdad.

Their opinions were surveyed according to a questionnaire prepared for this purpose, and the obtained opinions were analyzed in statistical analysis programs (SPSS) and (AMOS). Among the most prominent results are the weakness of company employees' interaction with electronic reservation programs and other digital mechanisms, and the work is limited to a limited range of mechanisms and technologies, while tourism companies globally have become one of the most absorbing organizations of the outputs of modern and advanced technical operations.

The most prominent recommendations are summarized in the need for administrations in tourism companies to establish an internal organizational culture based primarily on a state of cooperation and the dominance of the spirit of work based on self-denial and joint work in all details. The independence of departments in tourism companies does not mean that work is carried out in a state of estrangement among its employees.

A study (Samir, 2023) aimed to identify the availability of core competencies among faculty members at Dohuk Polytechnic University and their impact on achieving strategic flexibility.

Therefore, it was necessary to answer the following research question: What is the role of core competencies in achieving strategic flexibility? To verify the contents of the answer, Dohuk Polytechnic University was chosen as the field of study. The study sample included faculty members at the college, Duhok Technical Administrative Institute, and Shekhan Technical Institute, numbering (50) faculty members. The study adopted the descriptive analytical approach, and the questionnaire was considered the main tool for collecting the required data, which was analyzed using the statistical package (SPSS). The study reached a set of conclusions, most notably the existence of a significant impact relationship between the dimensions of core competencies in achieving strategic flexibility, which was relied upon in presenting the proposals consistent with it.

The study (Al-Azzawi and Al-Taie: 2022) The topic of (core capabilities and organizational change) is one of the important topics due to the contemporary business environment witnessing a series of technological changes and developments and an increase in the intensity of competition. The research was based on several questions that expressed the research problem.

The aim of answering them was to identify the reality of the research variables in the organization under study and to identify the relationship and impact between the research variables. To achieve this, two main hypotheses were formulated from which a group of sub-hypotheses emerged. The results revealed the existence of a correlation and influence of core capabilities with their sub-dimensions on organizational change in the organization under study. The researcher finally presented a set of recommendations to the organization under study, based on the results he reached, the most important of which are the following: Emphasizing the consolidation of the culture of teamwork because it is one of the most important dimensions of core capabilities in the organization under study, and encouraging employees in the organization under study who hold diplomas and bachelor's degrees in administrative and technical specializations to complete their postgraduate studies inside and outside Iraq, and the necessity of adopting a flexible organizational structure that guarantees the relationship between organizational change and core capabilities, in which the powers and tasks are specific and clear and there is broad participation. For the organization's employees.

The study (Al-Khalayleh and Al-Saed: 2019) aimed to identify the impact of core competencies on organizational performance in Jordanian commercial banks. The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach to deal with the data describing the research community. The questionnaire was used to collect data related to the study variables, where the data related to the study variables were collected and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) program. The researcher drew a stratified random sample so that the study sample consisted of (212) heads of departments, department managers, and section heads working in the following banks: (Arab Bank, Housing Bank, Bank of Jordan, and Cairo Amman Bank). The study concluded that there is a statistically significant effect at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) for core competencies in its dimensions (knowledge, skills, abilities, and facilities)

on organizational performance in its dimensions (customer satisfaction, internal processes, learning and growth) in Jordanian commercial banks. The study recommended the necessity for Jordanian commercial banks to pay attention to competent employees as a strategic asset, by giving them more incentives to retain them, and subjecting them to more training programs.

A study (Al-Rubaie et al., 2019) indicated that in a highly competitive market, core competency has emerged as a pivotal concept for competitive strategy. Core competency is the body of knowledge that distinguishes a company and provides a competitive advantage over others. The primary objective of this study was to examine the relationship between core competency, competitive advantage, and organizational performance. Core competency was measured through three dimensions: shared vision, collaboration, and empowerment. Competitive advantage was also measured through flexibility and responsiveness. The proposed model was tested in the context of the paint industry in the United Arab Emirates. The survey was administered electronically to a total of 77 managers. The results indicate that the measures appear consistent and reliable. The results indicate that while core competency has a strong and positive impact on competitive advantage and organizational performance, competitive advantage also has a significant impact on organizational performance. The results confirm the varying importance of core competency dimensions on competitive advantage and organizational performance. Flexibility was also found to have a greater impact on organizational performance than responsiveness. To maintain competitiveness and gain competitive advantages, managers can attempt to improve organizational performance by managing each dimension of core competency—that is, shared vision, collaboration, and empowerment.

Conceptual framework of the research

Business organizations of all types and specializations face numerous major environmental challenges and threats resulting from intense competition and the diversity of tasks assigned to them. Due to the demand for them to confront these challenges forcefully without significant losses, many modern behavioral and strategic concepts have emerged, most notably core competencies, strategic leadership, and organizational success. These concepts are among the most prominent philosophical approaches to management and organization, upon which organizations can be based in developing them and expanding opportunities for improving performance in all areas, seeking to satisfy the stakeholders who benefit from their services. Therefore, attention to core competencies has become of great importance in the various operational processes of organizations.

Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a set of individual or social behaviors, beliefs, and values adopted by a group of people in a specific environment or organization. It serves as a moral code among individuals, integrating behaviors and actions within it into a single, unified behavioral pattern. This code creates a common language for behavior, guiding it to serve its mission and purpose and the community in which it operates (Stephen & Robbins, 2012).

1. Clan Culture

This is a culture that focuses on people and the friendly relationships between them. It focuses on the internal work environment and flexibility in adapting to changes. (Cameron & Quinn, 2006) Clan culture focuses on relationships, team building, commitment, promoting human development, participation, mentoring, and training. (Stephen & Robbins, 2012)

- Commitment:
 - . The organization is a highly personal place. It is like a family, with employees sharing friendly relationships among themselves.
 - . Team Management (building effective, cohesive, and agreed-upon teams)
 - . The cohesion that binds the organization together is loyalty and mutual trust. Commitment to this organization is high.
- Openness:
 - . Leadership in the organization is generally viewed as an example of direction or facilitation; people seem to share a lot of themselves.
 - . The organization emphasizes human development. High trust, openness, and participation persist.
 - . The organization defines success based on human resource development, teamwork, employee commitment, and concern for people.

2. Developmental Culture

A dynamic, creative culture that focuses on the external work environment and flexibility in adapting to changes. (Cameron & Quinn, 2006) A developmental culture emphasizes creativity, innovation, envisioning the future, adapting to change, taking risks, breaking out of the norm, experimentation, and entrepreneurship (Stephen & Robbins, 2012).

- Adaptability:
 - . Leadership in the organization is generally viewed as the embodiment of entrepreneurship, innovation, or risk-taking.
 - . Future Management (communicating a clear vision for the future). □ The organization defines success based on its unique or cutting-edge products.
- Collaboration:
 - . The organization is a highly dynamic, entrepreneurial place. People are willing to take risks.
 - . The cohesion that binds the organization together is a commitment to innovation and development. There is a focus on being at the forefront.
 - . The organization emphasizes acquiring new resources and creating new challenges. Trying new things and exploring opportunities is valued.

3. Hierarchical Culture

A culture that focuses on processes and organizations, focusing on the internal work environment and maintaining the stability and consistency of the organization. (Cameron & Quinn, 2006) A hierarchical culture emphasizes efficiency, cost and process control, organizational improvement, technical expertise, mastery, problem-solving, error elimination, managerial analysis, and careful decision-making (Stephen & Robbins, 2012).

- Continuity:
 - . Leadership in the organization is generally viewed as the embodiment of a no-nonsense, results-oriented focus.
 - . The cohesion that holds an organization together is formal rules and policies. This is important for maintaining a smooth-running organization.
 - . The organization emphasizes continuity and stability. Efficiency, control, and smooth operations are important.
- Control:
 - . The organization is a highly structured and organized place. Formal procedures generally govern what people do.
 - . Management of the control system (the presence of measurement, monitoring, and stability systems)
 - . The organization defines success based on efficiency. Reliable delivery, smooth scheduling, and low-cost production are critical.

4. Rational Culture

A competitive, results-oriented culture that focuses on the external work environment and maintaining the stability and consistency of the organization. (Cameron & Quinn, 2006) A rational culture emphasizes value delivery, competition, achieving goals and results, making decisions quickly, confronting obstacles, directing, controlling, and getting things done quickly (Stephen & Robbins, 2012).

- Achievement:
 - . Leadership in an organization is generally considered an example of efficient coordination, organization, and smooth operation.
 - . The cohesion that binds the organization together is the focus on achievement and goal attainment.
 - . The organization emphasizes competitive actions and achievement. Achieving stretch goals and winning in the marketplace is paramount.

- Productivity:
 - . The organization is highly results-oriented. People are highly competitive and achievement-oriented.
 - . Competitiveness management (promoting an aggressive approach to outperforming competitors, high demands)
 - . The organization defines success based on winning in the marketplace and outperforming the competition.

Total Quality Management for Organizations

The term "quality" is difficult from an administrative and technical perspective, as it encompasses a wide range of characteristics and features. Achieving it at the professional level requires extensive technical expertise and highly specialized capabilities. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO 9000) emphasizes that quality is a set of distinctive characteristics present in a product or service that correspond to and meet specific needs, implicit desires, and exciting aspirations.

Conversely, it is unanimously agreed that quality is a specific, measurable characteristic necessary to meet customer expectations, as well as ensuring that products or services are free of any deficiencies or shortcomings that undermine customer satisfaction and loyalty to the organization. Today, quality is no longer defined by products, services, and the specifications required for them; it has become an integrated system encompassing all parts of a business organization. Its achievement requires the involvement of all employees, regardless of their level, from senior management to all members on the customer-facing lines. 6

In any case, Total Quality Management (TQM) reflects an integrated system of work in human resource management that focuses on raising customer satisfaction and seeks to reduce production, operations, and service costs across functions, departments, administrations, groups, and work teams, encompassing everyone, as noted above, from top to bottom. It also encompasses the supply chain, customers, and added value. Since the 1940s, numerous scientific approaches to quality have emerged, adopted by Western thinkers and scholars, as detailed in Figure (10), as follows: (Hammoud, 2000: 33); (Mishra, 2006: 16); (Foster, 2001: 42); (Al-Sarayrah and Al-Assaf, 2008: 12); (Gryna, 2007: 10); (NQAAC, 2004); (Sivla & Salles, 2002: 6).

The concept of organizational success

"organizational performance," commonly used by business administration researchers, refers to the outcomes achieved through the total exchange of an organization's activities with its resources, and its effective ability to attract competent human resources to achieve the desired expected outcomes. Organizational performance has been defined as "the final outcome of an organization's activities and a reflection of its ability to utilize human, material, financial, and information resources to achieve its desired goals" (Al-Mahna, 2012: 39).

Abu Rukba (2013) defined organizational performance as “the organization’s ability to achieve its goals by using available resources in an effective and efficient manner.” Kotler (2000:40) presented his concept of organizational performance as “reflecting the organization’s effectiveness and efficiency in achieving its short- and long-term goals, with the necessity of responding to environmental changes, in order to achieve satisfactory results that outperform its competitors, while emphasizing the consideration of four considerations that lead to achieving success in organizational performance, which are:

Identify stakeholders: customers, employees, suppliers, owners, etc. Understanding and realizing the importance of meeting their needs, desires, and expectations, each according to his purpose and the extent of his influence on the organization. Managing core business processes (developing new products, attracting new customers, reducing spending, reducing costs, etc.) to enable the organization to achieve stakeholder objectives and satisfy them.

Appropriate allocation of human, material, financial and information resources, and their implementation in the appropriate fields and operations required by the organization with all its various formations and units, and according to the established plan. Thinkers and researchers have differed in defining the criteria for organizational success. Business organizations have taken upon themselves the dimensions of effectiveness and efficiency as the basis for their success in an external environment with its rapidly changing and volatile forces and factors, as well as ensuring their survival, which largely depends on their development and growth. In the Arabic language, success often means achieving the desired goal with excellence and achieving outstanding results. In the English language, and based on well-known dictionaries such as (Baalbaki and Webster), "Success" means a high status, and comes from the word "Najah" (the persistent person succeeded or accomplished a successful task). As for the word "Successful", it means achieving a high status, achieving a preferred end, or reaching sublimity and elevation.

However, organizational success is still shrouded in much ambiguity, confusion over the clarity of its standard dimensions, organizational features, and procedural areas. The most prominent evidence of this is the multiplicity of concepts that have appeared in the literature of researchers and administrative thought regarding organizational success, including, for example: competitive success, strategic success, long-term success, leadership success, and operational success. According to the researcher's belief, for the purposes of the current study, they all fall under the concept of organizational success as a comprehensive, inclusive, and satisfactory concept for measuring the successful achievement of objectives without any unnecessary losses worth mentioning.

Many books, studies and research paved the way for the concept of organizational success according to the second idea above and adopted it, and worked on applying it in practical reality based on what he did in collecting facts about that (Al-Rikabi, 2004: 328), including the studies of the researcher in organizational theory (Steers) in the mid-seventies of the twentieth century, which combined many approaches to explain effectiveness, and arrived at a new developed approach called "multivariate measurement of effectiveness", in order to help in understanding and analyzing the internal processes of the organization, and arriving at an integrated concept of its success. He specifically indicated that organizational success is represented by the

dimensions of effectiveness and efficiency. Hitt (2001 : 101) et al) presented ; (2005:1) (Roger, a logical justification stating that looking at the success of a business organization through financial performance, operational efficiency, productivity, achieving profit or target return, or implementing some improvement programs within the framework of total quality management, process re-engineering, and benchmarking) is a narrow view that does not renew long-term success in the competitive market, as all of them can be simply imitated, transferred, or copied .

The definition of organizational success has received many intellectual interventions. Daft (2001:261) defined it as the organization's ability to manage knowledge, experiences, ideas, and the successful and accurate analysis of its memory, history, and heritage. This may only be achieved through effective knowledge management that seriously engages with markets and seizes new opportunities to achieve its goals in a timely manner. He believes that success depends on the existence of a long-term strategic vision to attract advanced technology, expand market share, and diversify local funding sources. Therefore, the secret of success lies in the organization's capable ability to manage its human resources in a way that is difficult for competitors to imitate or copy, with its growing ability to implement continuous change, select competent employees and involve them in decision-making, in addition to training and educating them to develop their skills, and providing them with adequate incentives.

Success (Waldron & Antonio, 2008, 153) is defined in almost the same sense as the previous one, as “the ability of a business organization to create value for competitors.” Al-Rikabi (2004) has a slightly different view than other researchers, as he asserts that the concept of organizational success is an advanced stage towards the concept of strategic success, taking the effectiveness approach as the basis for the concept of organizational success. He defined strategic success as representing the organization's ability to survive, adapt and grow in the presence of the goals it seeks to achieve. Dell and Kramer (2003) believe that success is achieved through strategic compatibility, which is the key to effectiveness and efficiency, and is represented by the organization's ability to coordinate its activities across all its components and fields, and link them to a shared strategic vision with all stakeholders, while achieving their goals, each according to its position. In this regard, the successful organization is the one that begins to integrate effectiveness and efficiency together, and is supposed to be characterized by a set of characteristics that all contribute to achieving sufficient organizational flexibility and ensuring customer loyalty, and according to the description of (Al- Tamimi, 2009) they are the following:

- 1) and values are clearly defined and communicated to employees and stakeholders.
- 2) Analyzing the organization's procedural and operational processes, and ensuring the efficiency of organizational activities, events, and services.
- 3) Ensuring that the products and services provided to the market are consistent with the needs, desires and expectations of their beneficiaries.
- 4) Providing value addition through technological development and nurturing individual and collective creativity and innovation .

Research hypothesis testing

The results of hypothesis testing are discussed by presenting the direct and mediating effects, using the Path Modeling Multiple Regression Approach to test the main direct effects, and the bootstrapping technique to test the mediating effects (Hair, Hult , et., 2017 Ramaya et al., 2018).

The researcher used the standard bootstrapping process with (284) items representing the number of teachers responding to the questionnaire, to measure the significance of the path coefficients by extracting the values of the (t) test , and evaluating their significance level through a one -tailed distribution , based on Hair, ut et al. (2017), who indicated that in the case of conducting a one-tailed test (1), the significance level of its value at (0.01) is greater than or equal to (2.33), and at (0.05) it is greater than or equal to (1.65), while at (0.1) it is greater than or equal to (1.28). Therefore, any value less than what was proposed above is considered insignificant. Table (1) shows the results of all hypotheses.

Table (1): Results of testing the study hypotheses by testing the significance of path coefficients

a result The test	value Morale of probability	value t	error Standard Std Error	Beta value Standard Std Beta	Path of measured variables	hypothesis
	0.001	3,198	0.102	0.325	Human efficiency - < Organizational efficiency	1
	0.000	4.618	0.085	0.394	Human Efficiency <- Total Quality Management <-Organizational efficiency	3

Table (1) indicates the following:

a) There is no direct significant relationship between Organizational culture and organizational effectiveness according to the results ($\beta = p > 0.117$, $t = 0.892$, 0.10). That is, Organizational culture as an independent variable is not linked to an influential relationship in improving the effectiveness of private colleges. The reason for this, according to the researcher’s perspective, can be attributed to the existence of a clear deficiency in the vision of senior management regarding long-term results, as reflected in some personal interviews conducted with a number of instructors, as strategic thinking is still low among them, and strategic plans are viewed as It is a case of fantasy that will not be realized in the future due to the high threats facing private colleges in Iraq. In this case, the first hypothesis (H1) proposed in the study methodology is rejected. There is a direct positive relationship with significant moral significance between Organizational culture and organizational efficiency ($\beta = 0.117$, $p > 0.10$) This means that by increasing successful practices to explore core competencies in private colleges, their efficiency in using available resources and working with exceptional effort and high perseverance by instructors increases to raise their reputation in the higher education environment in Iraq, in addition to increasing their loyalty and satisfaction with their jobs. In this case, the second hypothesis (2) proposed in the study methodology is accepted.

The core competencies of senior management have a strong direct significant relationship with TQM ($R = 0.840$). $35.699 = p < 0.01$, t). More precisely, it means that there are effective practices for selecting human competencies in private colleges that can strongly support the issue of total quality management and all its elements in terms of increasing commitment and commitment to its implementation, high focus on customers, activating continuous improvement of the educational process, involving instructors in various quality activities, and strengthening their education and training opportunities. In this case, the third hypothesis (3) proposed in the study methodology is accepted.

Based on the above, the model parameters (β) indicate the presence of a positive effect of exploring core competence on the dimensions of organizational success (individually and collectively). The null hypothesis of the main hypothesis regarding the dimension of exploring core competences and organizational success in the presence of total quality management was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was accepted, which is the presence of a positive effect of exploring core competence on the dimensions of organizational success (individually and collectively) in the presence of total quality management. The null hypothesis was accepted that there is a direct positive relationship with significant significance between Organizational culture and organizational efficiency. The third hypothesis was accepted, which indicates that the core competencies of senior management have a strong direct and significant relationship with total quality management.

RESEARCH CONCLUSION

This section presents the most important conclusions reached by the study as a result of the scientific and civil contributions made to the economic, social and cultural sector of Iraqi society, represented by private colleges that fall under the umbrella of higher education and scientific research. The study reached the following conclusions: First: Research conclusions.

- 1) It achieved a very high response from the faculty members in the Iraqi private colleges by filling it out. The questionnaire and the real response to the researcher, which was consistent with the recommendations of thinkers and researchers in the field of research measurement and evaluation, and I pointed out its objectivity, and the possibility of relying on it in measuring the phenomenon of exploring core competencies and their connection to both total quality management, and providing scientific knowledge to other researchers in the same specialization to conduct similar studies in other research communities.
- 2) In the study, no missing values were found from the data collection when the researcher completed the questionnaire to measure the variables (strategic leadership, total quality management, and organizational success), which indicates the strength and suitability of the tests used in the adopted conceptual model, and the achievement of vital areas for benefiting from its extracted results for the purposes of scientific research, and providing cognitive addition to science and society together.
- 3) The emergence of a significant influence of the five-point Likert scale used to measure the responses of the sample of teachers on all questionnaires without leaving any question

incomplete, in accordance with the limits of the study, taking into account accuracy and objectivity in analyzing data and developing the scale for the purposes of scientific research, and benefiting from it in other research to complete the scientific journey in the same specialty or one close to it by introducing other behavioral or strategic variables.

- 4) The relationship between exploring core competence and its impact on the dimensions of organizational success (individually and collectively), as the study indicated the presence of a positive impact of exploring core competence on the dimensions of organizational success (individually and collectively) in the presence of total quality management.
- 5) There is a direct, positive, and significant relationship between Organizational culture and organizational efficiency.
- 6) The core competencies of senior management have a strong, direct, and moral connection to total quality management.

Second: Recommendations

It is necessary to strike a balance between the internal work environment and external borrowing in order to maintain competent human resources, as human competence helps Iraqi community colleges achieve sustainable competitiveness. Encourage academic and administrative staff in the colleges under study to develop their skills by motivating them to enroll in development courses that add value to their existing knowledge. These courses should contribute to their advancement to higher administrative levels.

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